

Effect^a of pesticide application on N transformation in flooded rice fields at Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	NH ₄ -N (ppm)				NO ₃ + NO ₂ N (ppm)			
	2 d	5 d	10 d	20 d	2 d	5 d	10 d	20 d
Control	647	348	124	16	350	622	828	954
Lindane at 1.5 kg ai/ha	756	480	210	18	246	480	785	932
Carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	656	474	136	21	348	511	862	948
FMC 35001 at 0.75 kg ai/ha	697	498	142	28	282	498	854	954
Butachlor at 1.5 kg ai/ha	723	504	199	19	260	478	780	921
SE	27	38	41	7	23	35	28	20
CD (P = 0.05%)	79	112	—	—	68	104	—	—

^aAt 2, 5, 10, and 20 days after incubation.

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Calcium peroxide as a source of oxygen in flood-prone rice areas

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A 1979 field experiment studied the effect of calcium peroxide on plant stand of direct-seeded puddled rice varieties Saket 4 and UPR82. Seeds coated with calcium peroxide (60% by weight of seed) were compared with uncoated seeds. Sowing was in 5-10 cm standing water and the water level maintained for

Effect of CaO₂ seed coating on grain yield of direct-seeded puddled rice, 1979 wet season, Pantnagar, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Saket 4 - CaO ₂ coating	5.6 a
Saket 4 - no coating	3.7 bc
UPR82 - CaO ₂ coating	4.7 ab
UPR82 - no coating	2.2 c

^a Means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

the first 15 days, Calcium peroxide significantly increased grain yield of both varieties (see table and figure). ■

Effect of CaO₂ coating on plant stand. Pantnagar, India.

Environment and its influence

Effect of sheath blight infection on respiration and transpiration of rice plants

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The effect of sheath blight infection caused by *Corticium sasakii* (Shirai) Matsumoto [*Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk] on respiration and transpiration of rice plants was observed.

Seventy-two-day-old plants of the rice cultivar Pusa 2-21 were inoculated with a culture of *C. sasakii* grown on sterilized rice grain. Respiration was measured by a Warburg manometer at

30° C. One hundred grams of sheath and leaf tissues in 2-ml citrate buffer was placed in a flask and 0.2 ml 20% KOH in the center well. The experiment was repeated. One day after inoculation the rate of respiration in the diseased plants decreased (difference in manometric pressure 23.5 mm in diseased tissues against 21.5 mm in healthy tissues).

Sixty-two-day-old plants of the same cultivar grown in pots were carefully uprooted and kept in specimen bottles filled with water. After 2 days, the plants were inoculated as described above. The surface water was sealed by a layer of oil and the plants were kept outdoors under direct sun for 4 hours. Loss of water during transpiration was recorded by

noting the difference in weight of the whole assembly in this 4-hour period. The experiment was repeated and observations were taken up to 3 days at 1-day intervals. The average loss of water in the diseased and healthy leaves, respectively, was found to be 0.115 and 0.137 mg/hour per mm² after 1 day, 0.107 and 0.160 mg/hour per mm² after 2 days, and 0.110 and 0.120 mg/hour per mm² after 3 days, i.e. transpiration in the diseased plants was reduced and the reduction was greater after 2 days than after 1 or 3 days.

Therefore, because of sheath blight infection, respiration in the diseased rice plant increased but transpiration decreased. ■